

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A475

9 September 1996

OXICOA — TACIA

ADDENDUM

The correct dates for each of the flights are as follows:-

475	9 September 1996
476	10 September 1996
477	11 September 1996
478	13 September 1996
479	16 September 1996
480	17 September 1996
481	19 September 1996

TACIA OXICOA AUG-SEPT 96 Flight Summary

Prepared by: Andrew Kaye and Hannah Richer

[1] A475 9/9/96 TACIA TEST FLIGHT 1 2 hr 40 min

A short test flight for the chemistry instrumentation was carried out. The ozone, peroxide and formaldehyde instruments performed well. PAN was found to be below the detection limit of the GC's. The CO instrument did not work well (showing a large variability in background measurements). After initial concerns about the NO background, the NO_x instrument was found to operate satisfactorily on the two available channels (NO and NO₂).

An anticyclone centred to the west of the UK provided possible TACIA type weather. However, delays, due to incomplete airworthiness certification, meant that there was insufficient time to search for plumes from the UK. However, a small local plume was encountered in the Bristol Channel (51.36N, 4.12E).

Data from this flight could possibly be used to validate emission data from South Wales.

[2] A476 10/9/96 TACIA TEST FLIGHT 2 4 hr 30 min

Instruments performed as in the previous test flight: The ozone, peroxide and formaldehyde instruments performed well. PAN was found to be below the detection limit of the GC's. The CO instrument did not work well (showing a large variability in background measurements). The NO background had improved and the NO_x instrument was generally found to operate well on the two channels (NO and NO₂). However, on reaching maximum altitude difficulties were encountered on controlling the flow rate in the NO₂ channel.

A persistent anticyclone centred to the west of the UK again provided TACIA type conditions. However, delays, due to instrument requirements, meant that there was limited time to search for plumes from the UK. However, cross wind runs were carried out at an interval of approximately 60 miles along the SW coast. Trajectory analysis is to be carried out to determine whether the same air mass was sampled twice. However, no particularly notable plumes could be distinguished from the ozone, carbon monoxide and formaldehyde data. However, useful background information was obtained.

[3] A477 11/9/96 OXICOA Airmass characterization Flight 6 hr 00 min

The presence of an occluded frontal system over Norway/North Sea facilitated the study of three different airmasses.

Profiles were successfully flown on both sides of the warm front, but there was not sufficient time to travel to the northern edge of the cold frontal surface. However the lowest levels of the second stack may have been north of the front.

Ozone, formaldehyde and PAN instruments worked well, but the CO background problem was not corrected and the NO_x NO₂ channel flow problem had not been resolved.

[4] A478 11/9/96 TACIA TEST FLIGHT 3 2 hr 56 min

Thursday 12 September was used to install the NO_y converters and rectify the CO instrument. The CO work was successful. However the NO_y converters took longer than expected to complete. This resulted in a delayed take off.

Although primarily a TACIA instrument test flight the opportunity was taken to characterise the Arctic Maritime air mass over the North Sea. This effectively completed the work started on A477.

The chemistry kit performed as well as could be expected given the reduced warm up times available. The ozone pump switched off unexpectedly during the flight which caused a loss of data until the problem was identified.

[5] A479 11/9/96 TACIA 5 hr 40 min

There was a high pressure centred over the North Sea on this day which gave rise to continental outflow in the south-west approaches.

A very successful trial of the TACIA flying pattern, with two stacks being flown to sample continental air. A double inversion (875 and 950 mbar) was identified effectively capping pollutants and isolating them from the ocean surface sinks. Elevated levels of aerosol, CO (170 ppb), NO (40 ppt), NO₂ (400 ppt) and O₃ (65 ppb) were noted in this layer. Another interesting parcel of air was also sampled at higher altitudes (6 - 8 km). This air parcel was characterised by high levels of CO and aerosol. All the chemistry instrumentation performed well and the flight will provide a valuable contribution to the TACIA experiment.

[6] A480 11/9/96 OXICOA Airmass characterization Flight 6 hr 04 min

An anticyclone was centred to the north of the North Sea, such that continental plumes from northern Europe were reaching southern England across the North Sea. The same anticyclone was investigated during flight A479, at which time the high was centred over the UK.

The aim of this flight was to characterise air parcels within the anticyclone: both air parcels with recent continental influence and those with mainly marine back trajectories were studied. The highest pollutant concentrations of the campaign were measured during this flight in the boundary layer near Boscombe Down and in the marine boundary layer in the southern North Sea.

The marine boundary layer was distinct from the rest of the troposphere by a low level inversion. A slightly higher inversion was also apparent in profiles carried out north of 54 N. Interestingly, the seemingly typical vertical structure was not found in the southern North Sea: only the marine inversion was present.

A plume was encountered in the marine boundary layer at the first sampling region and elevated NO_x, NO_y and CO were observed with a corresponding decrease in ozone, indicating recent anthropogenic inputs. Profiles throughout the lowest 6000 ft of the atmosphere, whilst travelling northward, indicated some chemically aged parcels of air with elevated ozone, CO and NO_y. Haze layers were also visible. However, most of the air was generally clean. Further North, haze layers were less frequent, but layers with elevated ozone were still apparent. Elevated CO with a corresponding decrease in ozone indicated some recent pollution in the marine boundary layer at 57.2 N and 0.8 E.

All the chemistry instruments performed well during the flight. In particular, the peroxide measurements were found to show similar features to the calculated peroxide. Pitch, roll and yaw manoeuvres were carried out in order to test the NO_x inlets: preliminary results indicated that there were no large effects.

[7] A481 11/9/96 OXICOA Airmass characterization Flight/NOXY test 6 hr 16 min

An attempt was made at an airmass characterization flight. However, within an hour of take off, the peroxide and CO instruments had failed completely and the NO_x was only functioning at 50%. After consultation with the instrument operators it was decided that useful tests could still be carried with the operational NO_x channels and the flight plan was changed to a NO_x test flight. Several NILU and MRF bottles were also filled for analysis of hydrocarbons and possibly CO.

However, it is interesting to note that, at one point, air of stratospheric origin was encountered: we were frustrated by the lack of a complete suite of instruments. Recently polluted air and air which was chemically aged, as indicated by ratios of NO_x/NO_y and ozone, were both sampled. Useful data on emissions from north eastern Europe may have been gained.

FLIGHT FOLDER

DATE: 9/9/196 TAKE OFF 1335Z ~~H~~ (local time), FLIGHT NO. A475
 LANDING 1615Z

PROJECT OFFICER :

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST: H. RICHER

FLIGHT LEADER: M RILEY

OBSERVER: A KAYE

OTHERS:

M PICKERING

J. KENT

K JEWETT

D TIDDEMAN

C GERBIA + S KESSLER

S BAGUETTE

B BANDY

L GARDINAS

CAPTAIN: C D'BAEN

CO-PILOT: M PERSE

NAVIGATOR: J. CANNING.

ENGINEER: N. NEWTON

LOADMASTER: P. NIGHTINGALE

MPB

TRIALS INSTRUCTION (s):

OPERATING AREA:

South West / Bristol Channel.

GENERAL SYNOPTIC SITUATION:

TIME: 12Z

FLIGHT REPORT:

A475

133719 Take off from Boscombe

134426 (5) - 134953 (6)	PROFILE P1 ↗	3000ft - FL90	320/270°
134953 (6) - 141950 (7)	RUN 1	FL90	270°
141950 (7) - 144146 (10)	PROFILE P2 ↗	FL90 - FL250	270°
144336 (11) - 145334 (12)	RUN 2	FL250	120°
145334 (12) - 150332 (13)	PROFILE P3 ↘	FL250 - FL150	110°/035°
150332 (13) - 151331 (14)	RUN 3	FL150	030°
151331 (14) - 151715 (15)	PROFILE P4 ↘	FL150 - FL110	020°
151715 (15) - 152712 (16)	RUN 4	FL110	020°
152712 (16) - 153816 (19)	PROFILE P5 ↘	FL110 → 2500ft	090°
153816 (19) - 155315 (20)	RUN 5	2500ft	090/120°

161637 Land at Boscombe

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms:	Form Title
1 → 1 3 1 1	Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet + TACIA <i>new folder</i> Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements Interactive log
1 1 1 1	Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
	MCR log CCM log MARSS log Chemistry log
3	Particulate/Filter boom Operator's log ZDK/FSSP/Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)
1 1 1 1 1 1 1	Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Signal register Weather charts Satellite pictures Omega track Electronics pre-flight Mechanical fit

A475 09-SEP-96 Height time series

A475 09-SEP-96 13:44:26-15:53:15GMT

ins_track - fur 09

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A475 Date: 13.9.96 User: HI RICHER
Interactive by: M. RILEY
Date: 12.9.96.

Renav

GPS Nav degraded • 1430 → 1445 Z

TWC

Profile plotted :

Line chosen : Profile / Whole flight / Other

$$a = - 0.2935 E + 1$$

$$b = + 0.1506 E - 2$$

$$c = + 0.8756 E - 6$$

LWC

Heimann / Barnes

No calibrations done

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: H RICHER

Project: ^{1 AC111} TEST Date: 9/19/96

Flight No: 475 Page 1 of 3

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No
						Latitude	Longitude		
1-	1							TAKE OFF BOSCOMBE DOWN	
	2								
	3								
13:43	4		FL030					FL030 cloudy wet chem checks complete.	
13:43:35	5	P1						Flight level 30 → 90 coming out of cloud	
13:46:00			FL050					FL050 above 4/8 stratos boundary layer (cloud top FL050 800ft)	
13:49:00	6	R1	FL090					FL090 BLUE SKY ABOVE	
14:04:00			FL090					FL090 1/8 CIRRUS ABOVE	
14:05:28			FL090					CLOUD THINNING BELOW TO 6/8 O ₃ , CO, H ₂ O ₂ CONSTANT ON RUN.	
14:15:40			FL090					O ₃ increased 10%, CO decreasing, throughout run. H ₂ O ₂ increasing, CH ₂ O decreasing	
14:17:00			FL090					OVER SEA CLOUD QUITE THIN 3/8	
14:19:49	7	P2						START PROFILE P2 FL090 - FL260	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: H. RICHOL

Project: ⁷²⁵⁷TRIA
Flight No: 475

Date: 9/9/96
Page 2 of 3

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
14:24:30	7	7				50.61 -5.92	1/8 CIRRUS ABOVE VARIABLE CLOUD BELOW.		
							PEAKS IN CO 2 O3 AT 3000 - 3500 M + 4500 - 5500 M		
							PEROXIDE PROFILE INTERESTING. UP TO 2PPB UP TO 4000 M decreasing above.		
							CH ₂ O VERY REGULAR THROUGHOUT PROFILE		
14:42:00	10		FL250			50.4 -8.1	END OF PROFILE P1 FL260		
14:43:36	11	R2				50.38 -8.09	START OF RUN 2. (ZERO of H ₂ O ₂ carried out).		
14:43:36							1/8 CIRRUS ABOVE BROKEN CLOUD (cu) BELOW		
14:53:30	12	R3				50.11 -7.0	START FL250 → FL150		
14:59:00			FL200		003	49.99 -6.49	CHANGE HEADING		
15:00:53			FL180		035	49.96 -6.35	CHANGE HEADING		
15:03:30	13	R3	FL150		029	50.07 -6.26	START RUN 3. FL150		
15:13:31	14	R4			014	50.62 -6.01	PROFILE TO FL110.		

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: H RICHUR

Project: ~~ATIS~~ ^{MACIA} Date: 9/9/96
 Flight No: A475 Page 3 of 3

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (cg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
15:17:18	15	4	FL110		015	50.81	-5.96	4/8 cloud below Cu & STCU O ₃ up to 45 PPB. → 52 PPB	
15:23			FL110		014	51.16	-5.86	APPEAR TO GO OUT OF O ₃ PLUME 15:23 THAN IMMEDIATELY BACK IN?	
15:27:12	16	R4			085	51.35	-5.77	TURN ONTO HEADING. END OF RUN 4 PROFILE TO FLO30	
15:27:21	17	P5				51.35	-5.71	PROFILE TO FLO30 O ₃ peak 15:29:44, some CO peaks.	
15:34:09	8		5000ft FL110			51.35	-5.25	ENTERING CLOUD (FLO40) CHANGE FROM 1000ft/min to 500ft/min	
15:35:00			4000ft FL110		085	51.35	-5.2	ENTER CLOUD INVERSION (STRONG) 875mb	
15:37:31			3000ft FL110		085	51.35	-5.02	PROFILE CONTINUED TO 2500 TO cpt below cloud	
15:38:16	19	R5	2500ft FL110		085	51.35	-4.93	STILL IN VERY BOTTOM OF CLOUD	
15:46:19			"		"	51.36	-4.12	CO, O ₃ ANTICORRELATION, H ₂ O ₂ LOW. LOTS CO, BOTTLES FILLED, LOTS NO _x !	
15:53:29	20	R5/P6	2500ft		108	51.35	-3.73	END RUN 5 / START P6	
15:55:45		P6			108	51.32	-3.61	O ₃ INCREASING OUT OF BL CO DECREASING.	
15:59		R7	7000ft			51.1	-3		

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: A475

Date: 9.9.96

A/S Name: H. RICHIE

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for S. UFA ... KFA ... HANNAH
2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period
3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of Project TACIA
4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long? 2 years
5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?
6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in? .. MRFIL : MRP
7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

VIDEO TAPE LOG

Flight No A 475.....

Project TACIA.....

Date 9.9.96.....

Tape No A475..... User H. RICHER.....

Retention Period 2 years.....

GMT	Tape Counter	Camera Position	Remarks
135850	0000	FFC	START RECORDING
→ 141950	"	"	RUN 1, FL90
141950 → 144146	"	"	PROFILE P2 ↗, FL90 - FL250
144336 → 145334	"	"	RUN 2, FL250
145334 → 150332	"	"	PROFILE P3 ↓, FL250 - FL150
150332 → 151331	"	"	RUN 3, FL150
151331 → 151715	"	"	PROFILE P4 ↓, FL150 - FL110
151715 → 152712	"	"	RUN 4, FL110
162751 → 153816	"	"	PROFILE P5 ↓, FL110 - 2500ft
153816 → 155315	"	"	RUN 5, 2500ft
161637			Land at Boscombe
162103			STOP RECORDING.

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A475 Date: 9.9.96

Page...!...of 1

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1342	REF +	5	567	✓		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2854	✓		Approx 3071 2850	
	AOSS	19	1608	Noisy F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	1061	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	2139	27	2700 ft	As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	3545			As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	1381				
	A/S	9				As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	1914				
	UP2S	82	1514				
JND	UIRS	83	933				
	UP1Z	84	156	✓		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	152			Approx 0149	
	URZ	86	946			Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2616			As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2625			As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0			As IAT	
	LP1S	91	1490				
	LP2S	92	1105				
JND	LIRS	93	865				
	LP1Z	94	153	✓		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	163	✓		Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	880			Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	2628			As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2601			As IAT	
	LIRT	99	0			As IAT	
	J/W	42	1143			As Indicated 0000	
	NEPH	47					
	HYGR	58	1933	-	-17.9 C		
	HYCC	59	1152			696-901	
	FDEW	138	594			DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	992				
	DTF	10	3002				
	DTC	11	5				
	NDTF	23	2677		+11.0	same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	5				
	INCT	48		2077	HEIM		
	GEN	140		2394	PRTC	less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70	1540			0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	1365			0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	144				
	O3P	106	2043			$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3R	113	1978				
			851				
			625				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1349	FL NO	1	Hex	1141	* *		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	309	* *		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	258	* *		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	6			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
	LATC	160	Dec	581		51.04	Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4063		-2.9	Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: FL90

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1352	TWCD	70	1595	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2559	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1379	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2768	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2233			2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	1388			0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2996			0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1021			0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4095			4095	
	EV1V	170	3477				
	EV2V	171	3141				
	NPWR	172	2669				
	EVIC	173	4013				
	EV2C	174	3995				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK Flight No: A475 Date: 9.9.96
for auto selection

Page...1...of 1

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1148	REF +	5	567	✓		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2854			Approx 3071 2857	
	AOSS	19	4095	PERF F/S STBD O/S	TORQUE 2.0	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	4095	UP F/S DOWN O/S	TORQUE 3.0	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	0	✓		As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	3905	1013/00	✓	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	4019	1013	✓		
	A/S	9	75	✓		As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	360	75	✓		
	UP2S	82	291	28	✓		
	UIRS	83	101	JN02			
	UP1Z	84	152	✓		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	146	✓		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	98	JN02		Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2482	+18	17	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2500	✓		As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0000	JN02		As IAT	
	LP1S	91	↑				
	LP2S	92					
	LIRS	93					
	LP1Z	94	4095			Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95				Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	↓			Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97				As IAT	
	LP2T	98				As IAT	
	LIRT	99				As IAT	
	J/W	42	996	0		As Indicated 0000	
	NEPH	47					
	HYGR	58	2713	74	✓		
	HYCC	59	722	✓		696-901	
	FDEW	138				DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139					
	DTF	10	220	+15	✓		
	DTC	11	6				
	NDTF	23	3980	+15	✓	same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	5				
	INCT	48		HEUM	2696		
	CCN	140		PRTC	2394	less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70				0000-4094	
	TSAM	72				0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	45				
	O3P	106	2033			$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3T	113	1695				
	O3F	114	971				
	HCHO	150	2613				

HEUM 141
PRTC 142

~~NEPH~~
 NPRS 175
 NTMP 176
 NBTS 177
 NGTS 178
 NRTS 179
 NBS 180
 NGBS 181
 NRBS 182
 NHUM 183
 NSTS 184

ORGP 151 114
 H202 152 53
 PLIN 185
 PLOG 186
 FIPL 195
 FIPLR 196

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex	1141			Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	290	1227		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	1826	1227:34		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	4	✓		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
	LATC	160	Dec	4094			Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4094			Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height:

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1249	TWCD	70	2909	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	1113	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	142	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2134	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2241	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2079	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2138	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1022	✓		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4089	✓		4095	
	EV1V	170	2042	✓			
	EV2V	171	2043				
	NPWR	172	3409				
	EVIC	173	3968				
	EV2C	174	3968				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	OFF/ On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Clear JMO		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	OFF/ On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Clear JMO		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A475

Date: 9/9/76

Operator: ML

Page 1 of 3

G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP		2D-C		HVPS/2D-P		REMARKS			
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Conc/cc	Max Size	Reff	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit		Conc/m ³	Max Size	Habit
14533	28	0.10										Start P1
14636	36	0.08										5000'
14746	45	0.09										6000'
14847	85	0.09										7000'
14956	0											8000'
15000	0											FL90' end R & L start Run 1
15100	0											
15200	0											
15300	0											
15400	0											
15500	0											
15600	0											
15700	0											
15800	0											
15900	0											
16000	0											
16100	1	0.08										
16200	8	0.07										
16300	1	0.07										
16400	30	0.10										
16500	37	0.10										
16600	35	0.10										
16700	35	0.10										
16800	38	0.09										
16900	38	0.09										
17051	35	0.10										end of Run 2 start P2
17149	10	0.09										FL100
17300	1	0.08										FL110
17357	1	0.08										FL120
17506	7	0.08										FL130
17600	13	0.09										FL140
17659	30	0.09										FL150
17804	25	0.10										FL160
17914	15	0.08										FL170
18029	10	0.08										FL180
18155	9	0.08										FL190
18350	9	0.09										FL200
18535	5	0.07										FL210
18730												FL220
												FL230

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT

=====

FLIGHT NO: A475

DATE: 11 / 9 / 96

MRF 13

INSTRUMENT	FITTED		OPERATED		COMMENTS
	YES	NO	YES	NO	
NAVIGATION:					
GPS					
OMEGA					
INU	✓				
RADALT					
THERMOMETERS:					
DI TEMP					
NDI TEMP		✓			
ICTP		x			
BARNES PRT4		Hein-om			
HYGROMETERS:					
GEN. EASTERN					
TWC		✓			
FWVS		✓			
J/W					
EXP. PITOT HEAD:					
STATIC PRESS.		✓			
PITOT PRESS.		✓			
GUST VANES					
RADIOMETERS:					
UPPER CLEAR		✓			
UPPER RED		✓			
UPPER SILICON		JN02			
LOWER CLEAR		✓			
LOWER RED		✓			
LOWER SILICON		JN02			
MARSS		✓			
MCR/SAFIRE		✓			
DEIMOS		✓			
CHEMISTRY:					
OZONE		✓			
ECGC		✓			
NOX Y		✓			
OTHERS:					
CCN		x			
CLOUD PHYSICS		✓			
CABIN PRESS		✓			
NEPHELOMETER		x			
HOLOGRAPHY		x			

P.T.O. FAULTS/INCIDENTS

1. AC BUS LOW lights flashing on flight deck when NOXY pumps switched on. Tried 2 other GPUs eventually condition went away. Cold start problem??
2. ER Horace display floating on/off. Tried patching ~~hor~~ out of vid sequencer. Still the same.
3. GPS Nav degraded. 1434
4. Peroxide ~~test~~
5. Satcom GPS speed = 000 sometimes 140 kts etc.
6. Inflight - gen loads higher than normal but NOT exceeding
7. NO - ~~test~~ trouble with flows.
8. HORACE Teph - can we have feet marked on 100mb verticals
9. FL Horace - no cloud phys display.
10. changed VIRS & LIRS to suit JNO2 scales
remembers to change them back at end of week.

VIR	-750	, +750	Upper	} original Nb. 1.
LIR	-750	+750	Lower	

A475 09-SEP-96 13:58:12 006 2 50.84 -3.39 FR P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knts	TAT C	DEW C	WIND
265.	725.	9.0	204.	3.1	-5.7	048/17

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A475

09-SEP-96

13:55:24

006 Q

50.92

-3.15 FR P

HDG degT 175.	SPR mb 722.	PHGT kft 9.1	TAS knots 213.	TAT C 3.7	DEW C -6.2	WIND deg m/s 045/15	
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=====

0000.00 0000.00 0000.00 0000.00 0000.00 0000.00 0000.00

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
-------------	-----------	-----------	---	---	---	------------	---

A475

09-SEP-96

14:02:12

006 Ω

50.81

-3.83 FR P

HDG deg T 266.	SPR mb 725.	PHGT kft 9.0	TAS knots 210.	TAT C 2.9	DEW C -5.6	WIND deg m/s 047/18	
----------------------	-------------------	--------------------	----------------------	-----------------	------------------	---------------------------	--

FEET -GT 2737.33 m 4202 MF 0.00 PP6 100 4202 2.17 PP6
 0.00 1.00 2.00 3.00 4.00 5.00

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
-------------	-----------	-----------	---	---	---	------------	---

HERSTMONCEUX

03882

AT 11Z

10	050	23
15	035	42
20	042	68
25	042	68
30	050	65
40	045	56
50	045	65
60	045	62
70	050	28
85	055	14
100		

MAX	MIL	9766
TRQP		050 73
		172 -68
		040 58
10		1638
15		1583
20		1207
25		1005
30		742
40		742
50		576
70		313
85		156
100		22

M	235.0
M	176.0
M	162.0
M	121.0
M	202.0
M	165.0
M	287.0
M	154.5
M	554.1
10	-57
15	-60
20	-61

CAMBORNE

03806

AT 11Z

10	050	20
15	065	11
20	055	58
25	055	69
30	045	44
40	045	65
50	055	39
60	055	60
70	050	60
85	050	31
100		

MAX	MIL	171 -69
TRQP		060 51
10		1639
15		1387
20		1213
25		1945
30		747
40		581
50		317
70		158
85		24
100		

M	252.0
M	174.0
M	162.0
M	122.0
M	202.0
M	166.0
M	292.4
M	134.2
M	556.8
10	-60
15	-62
20	-62

ABERFORTH

03502

AT 11Z

10	040	30
15	010	30
20	045	34
25	045	36
30	045	36
40	030	27
50	035	27
60	045	35
70	045	36
85	040	31
100	035	11

MAX	MIL	163 -70
TRQP		045 36
10		1644
15		1392
20		1218
25		1076
30		954
40		781
50		320
70		161
85		26
100		

M	252.0
M	174.0
M	162.0
M	122.0
M	203.0
M	167.0
M	261.2
M	283.9
M	538.1
10	-60
15	-63
20	-61

HERSBY

03496

AT 11Z

10	050	33
15	030	35
20	030	62
25	040	61
30	040	64
40	030	46
50	045	46
60	030	35
70	040	29
85	005	19
100		

MAX	MIL	11356
TRQP		035 68
		170 -68
		025 46
10		1636
15		1383
20		1207
25		1066
30		944
40		477
50		314
70		156
85		22
100		

M	253.0
M	176.0
M	161.0
M	122.0
M	201.0
M	166.0
M	263.4
M	511.7
M	554.8
10	-60
15	-61
20	-62

ASXX EGRR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 1200 UTC 09 SEP 1996

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:2000000

Revised and Green - by Geographic Service, New O 188. District - Meteorological Office, London W1A 0BZ. Copyright - Met Office, Crown Copyright 1996

A475.TXT

From 0Z 7/ 9/1996 to 15Z 9/ 9/1996

Arrows every 24 hrs

Plotted 28-Oct-1996 13:22

A475 09-SEP-96

P1 3000ft-FL90(134426-134953) + P2 FL90-FL250(141950-144146)

A475 09-SEP-96

P3 FL250-FL150(145334-150332) + P4 FL150-FL110(151331-151715)

A475 09-SEP-96

P5 FL110-2500ft(152712-153815)

A475 09-SEP-96 P1 3000ft-FL90 From 134426-134953 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:15

A475 09-SEP-96 P1 3000ft-FL90 From 134426-134953 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:15

A475 09-SEP-96 P1 3000ft-FL90 From 134426-134953 Plotted 14-01-1996 12:15

A475 09-SEP-96 R1 FL90 From 134953-141950 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:19

A475 09-SEP-96 R1 FL90 From 134953-141950 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:19

A475 09-SEP-96 R1 FL90 From 134953-141950 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:20

A475 09-SEP-96 R1 FL90 From 134953-141950 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:20

A475 09-SEP-96 R1 FL90 From 134953-141950 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:20

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 1798
Mean 725.591
Standard dev 0.695797
Max value 727.113
Min value 723.388

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 1798
Mean 276.543
Standard dev 0.227389
Max value 277.254
Min value 276.087

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 1798
Mean 266.088
Standard dev 2.00242
Max value 267.788
Min value 258.281

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 1798
Mean 37.3262
Standard dev 4.86496
Max value 48.7268
Min value 29.9017

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 1798
Mean 12.3750
Standard dev 18.2278
Max value 77.0726
Min value 0.000000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 1798
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 1798
Mean 2728.90
Standard dev 7.59326
Max value 2752.95
Min value 2712.31

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 1798
Mean 50.7793
Standard dev 0.132390
Max value 51.0712
Min value 50.6032

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 1798
Mean -4.14542
Standard dev 0.862878
Max value -2.73063
Min value -5.69108

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 1798
Mean -12.9685
Standard dev 1.07982
Max value -10.0929
Min value -15.5486

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 1798
Mean -13.4882
Standard dev 2.00336
Max value -9.34702
Min value -17.4755

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 1798
Mean -0.112072
Standard dev 0.588688
Max value 1.33344
Min value -1.71958

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 1798
Mean 18.7417
Standard dev 2.01054
Max value 22.4137
Min value 13.9989

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 46.1254

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 1798
Mean 108.521
Standard dev 2.11907
Max value 113.702
Min value 101.893

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 255.974

A475 09-SEP-96 P2 FL90-FL250 From 141950-144146 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:24

A475 09-SEP-96 P2 FL90-FL250 From 141950-144146 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:24

A475 09-SEP-96 R2 FL250 From 144336-145334 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:25

A475 09-SEP-96 R2 FL250 From 144336-145334 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:25

A475 09-SEP-96 R2 FL250 From 144336-145334 Plotted 14-01-1996 12:25

A475 09-SEP-96 R2 FL250 From 144336-145334 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:26

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 599
 Mean 377.852
 Standard dev 0.148268
 Max value 378.198
 Min value 377.420

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 599
 Mean 245.285
 Standard dev 0.117374
 Max value 245.541
 Min value 245.040

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 599
 Mean 237.097
 Standard dev 1.65025
 Max value 241.854
 Min value 234.197

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 599
 Mean 40.2416
 Standard dev 5.79846
 Max value 57.8181
 Min value 34.0194

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 599
 Mean 3.35100
 Standard dev 3.83534
 Max value 23.0075
 Min value 0.000000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 599
 Mean 0.000000
 Standard dev 0.000000
 Max value 0.000000
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 599
 Mean 7585.71
 Standard dev 2.74263
 Max value 7593.72
 Min value 7579.31

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 599
 Mean 50.2141
 Standard dev 7.526278e-02
 Max value 50.3616
 Min value 50.0973

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 599
 Mean -7.62409
 Standard dev 0.303188
 Max value -7.09853
 Min value -8.14064

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 599
 Mean -9.35801
 Standard dev 0.684528
 Max value -7.45482
 Min value -10.7913

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 599
 Mean -8.64876
 Standard dev 1.10634
 Max value -6.81173
 Min value -10.9827

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 599
 Mean -0.471077
 Standard dev 0.300727
 Max value 0.130379
 Min value -1.18011

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 599
 Mean 12.7589
 Standard dev 1.12925
 Max value 14.8895
 Min value 10.3526

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 42.7444

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 599
 Mean 138.618
 Standard dev 1.39153
 Max value 141.172
 Min value 132.970

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 111.611

A475 09-SEP-96 P3 FL250-FL150 From 145334-150332 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:27

A475 09-SEP-96 P3 FL250-FL150 From 145334-150332 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:27

A475 09-SEP-96 P3 FL250-FL150 From 145334-150332 Plotted 14-01-1996 12:27

A475 09-SEP-96 R3 FL150 From 150332-151331 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:29

A475 09-SEP-96 R3 FL150 From 150332-151331 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:29

A475 09-SEP-96 R3 FL150 From 150332-151331 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:29

A475 09-SEP-96 R3 FL150 From 150332-151331 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:29

A475 09-SEP-96 R3 FL150 From 150332-151331 *Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:29*

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 600
Mean 572.315
Standard dev 0.489255
Max value 573.888
Min value 571.106

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 600
Mean 266.453
Standard dev 0.217477
Max value 266.815
Min value 266.026

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 600
Mean 260.273
Standard dev 0.783594
Max value 261.741
Min value 256.935

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 600
Mean 42.1329
Standard dev 1.52226
Max value 44.9534
Min value 38.4169

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 600
Mean 24.7130
Standard dev 7.90865
Max value 78.0609
Min value 8.00078

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 600
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 600
Mean 4565.37
Standard dev 6.46500
Max value 4581.37
Min value 4544.60

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 600
Mean 50.3090
Standard dev 0.154979
Max value 50.5828
Min value 50.0518

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 600
Mean -6.13115
Standard dev 6.051157e-02
Max value -6.05103
Min value -6.26772

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 600
Mean -12.4658
Standard dev 0.558090
Max value -10.8304
Min value -13.7005

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 600
Mean -14.7617
Standard dev 0.497915
Max value -13.1339
Min value -15.7264

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 600
Mean -0.272403
Standard dev 0.654963
Max value 1.07537
Min value -1.38390

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 600
Mean 19.3292
Standard dev 0.494854
Max value 20.6505
Min value 18.1200

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 49.8200

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 600
Mean 118.819
Standard dev 1.43158
Max value 121.475
Min value 115.742

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 14.6129

A475 09-SEP-96 P4 FL150-FL110 From 151331-151715 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:30

A475 09-SEP-96 P4 FL150-FL110 From 151331-151715 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:30

A475 09-SEP-96 P4 FL150-FL110 From 151331-151715 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:30

A475 09-SEP-96 R4 FL110 From 151715-152712 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:32

A475 09-SEP-96 R4 FL110 From 151715-152712 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:32

A475 09-SEP-96 R4 FL110 From 151715-152712 Plotted 14-04-1996 12:32

A475 09-SEP-96 R4 FL110 From 151715-152712 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:32

A475 09-SEP-96 R4 FL110 From 151715-152712 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:32

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 598
Mean 670.524
Standard dev 0.473863
Max value 671.900
Min value 669.621

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 598
Mean 273.931
Standard dev 0.320191
Max value 274.513
Min value 273.370

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 598
Mean 262.748
Standard dev 3.34365
Max value 270.575
Min value 257.992

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 598
Mean 43.3331
Standard dev 6.24703
Max value 52.8484
Min value 32.9819

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 598
Mean 25.1018
Standard dev 11.7694
Max value 62.0383
Min value 2.00000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 598
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 598
Mean 3348.95
Standard dev 5.50914
Max value 3359.46
Min value 3332.96

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 598
Mean 51.0504
Standard dev 0.152970
Max value 51.3135
Min value 50.7866

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 598
Mean -5.92802
Standard dev 4.032983e-02
Max value -5.85875
Min value -5.99666

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 598
Mean -9.78657
Standard dev 0.576641
Max value -8.46303
Min value -10.8520

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 598
Mean -12.4014
Standard dev 0.818136
Max value -10.5499
Min value -14.7356

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 598
Mean 4.562847e-02
Standard dev 0.663939
Max value 1.98637
Min value -0.910133

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 598
Mean 15.8105
Standard dev 0.774900
Max value 17.7606
Min value 14.3179

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 51.7212

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 598
Mean 111.276
Standard dev 1.97674
Max value 115.478
Min value 108.285

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 9.35866

A475 09-SEP-96 P5 FL110-2500ft From 152712-153815 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:34

A475 09-SEP-96 P5 FL110-2500ft From 152712-153815 Plotted 14-01-1996 12:34

A475 09-SEP-96 P5 FL110-2500ft From 152712-153815 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:34

A475 09-SEP-96 R5 2500ft From 153816-155315 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:36

A475 09-SEP-96 R5 2500ft From 153816 - 155315 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:36

A475 09-SEP-96 R5 2500ft From 153816-155315 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:36

A475 09-SEP-96 R5 2500ft From 153816-155315 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:36

A475 09-SEP-96 R5 2500ft From 153816-155315 Plotted 14-Oct-1996 12:36

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 900
Mean 936.928
Standard dev 0.610017
Max value 938.177
Min value 933.543

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 900
Mean 281.448
Standard dev 0.128442
Max value 281.689
Min value 281.001

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 900
Mean 279.115
Standard dev 0.487822
Max value 280.186
Min value 277.920

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 900
Mean 29.7280
Standard dev 3.42857
Max value 36.1833
Min value 22.3076

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 900
Mean 645.953
Standard dev 115.434
Max value 990.064
Min value 351.958

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 900
Mean 0.107851
Standard dev 0.121461
Max value 0.524061
Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 900
Mean 793.655
Standard dev 5.96832
Max value 827.433
Min value 783.386

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 900
Mean 51.3489
Standard dev 1.025323e-02
Max value 51.3626
Min value 51.3292

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 900
Mean -4.39647
Standard dev 0.335648
Max value -3.81473
Min value -4.97517

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 900
Mean -3.74697
Standard dev 0.751964
Max value -1.42879
Min value -6.31866

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 900
Mean -6.52044
Standard dev 0.790084
Max value -4.23267
Min value -8.47734

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 900
Mean -0.111446
Standard dev 0.538257
Max value 2.31274
Min value -1.29780

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 900
Mean 7.55063
Standard dev 0.856172
Max value 9.51961
Min value 5.04403

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 60.1161

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 900
Mean 96.2413
Standard dev 2.23765
Max value 105.831
Min value 92.0751

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 88.3431

Glossary

Aircraft Position, Speed and Attitude

- **Navigation:** The aircraft carries GPS, OMEGA, and inertial navigation systems. Pitch and yaw are only displayed for flight A480, where specific manoeuvres were used to test the response of the NO_x inlets.
- **Pressure height:** is based on the standard atmosphere as specified by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (sea level pressure of 1013.25 hPa). Pressure height is quoted in terms of Flight Levels (height in hundreds of feet *e.g.* FL100 = 10000 feet).
- **Radar height:** altitude of the aircraft above surface, measured by radar.
- **Time:** All times are UTC.

General meteorology

- **Tephigrams:** are given for every major profile of each flight. A tephigram is a thermodynamic diagram (temperature (T) - entropy (ϕ) diagram) used to assess the static stability of a given atmospheric profile. Other meteorological organisations use similar diagrams such as the Emagram or the Skew T log p diagram.
- **Deiced true temperature:** air temperature with corrections for aircraft speed and altitude.
- **Potential temperature:** the temperature that a parcel of air would have if it follows a dry adiabatic lapse rate to the 1000 hPa level.
- **Dew point:** dew point (the temperature at which a sample of air would just become saturated with respect to a plane surface of water if cooled at a constant pressure) calculated from the chilled mirror General Eastern hygrometer.
- **FWVS Dew point:** dew point calculated by use of the Lyman- α spectroscopic instrument "the fluorescence water vapour sensor".

Cloud Physics

- **PCASP:** The Passive Cavity Aerosol Sampling Probe counts number concentrations (number per cm³) of particles in 15 channels spaced pseudo-logarithmically over the diameter range 0.10 μ m to 3.00 μ m, to provide a particle size distribution over this range.
- **FSSP:** The Forward Scattering Spectrometer Probe is used to measure water droplets in the size range 0.5 to 47.0 μ m diameter (cloud droplets). It has four range settings, each of which is divided into 15 size channels.

Chemistry Parameters

- **Ozone:** Calibrated readings from the TECO 49 ozone analyser in ppb. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent (UK Met. Office).
- **CO:** Raw data recorded in ppb. Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Stefan Kessler (KFA Julich).
- **JNO₂:** The sum of upward and downward facing radiometers (raw data). Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Stefan Kessler (KFA Julich).
- **Hydrogen peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb. Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Organic peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb. Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Modelled peroxide:** hydrogen peroxide concentrations as estimated from the concentrations of ozone and water vapour concentrations according to the following algorithm. The model is used in flight and is included in this data summary for individual scientists assessment of the use of algorithms for the purpose of in flight planning. Contact Brian Bandy, Claire Reeves (UEA, Norwich) or Dave Tiddeman (UK Met. Office) for details.

$$H_2O_2 = (k_3 j_4 [O_3][H_2O]) / (k_5 [M] (j_6 + k_7 + [OH] k_8))$$

where k_3 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O(^1D) + H_2O \rightarrow 2OH$

k_5 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O(^1D) + M \rightarrow O(^3P) + M$

k_8 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $OH + H_2O_2 \rightarrow H_2O + HO_2$

k_7 is the first order loss due to dry deposition. However, as the boundary layer is difficult to define, this term has been ignored for the time being.

j_4 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O_3 + h\nu \rightarrow O(^1D) + O_2$

j_6 is the rate coefficient for reaction: $H_2O_2 + h\nu \rightarrow OH + OH$

j_4 , j_6 and $[OH]$, calculated by a 2D model, are dependent upon latitude and time of year.

- **Formaldehyde:** Raw data recorded as bits. NB this instrument has a long time delay *ca.* 12 minutes. Instrument scientist: Laura Cardenas (UEA, Norwich).
- **NO_x:** Parameters were not recorded on MRF's data recording system and are therefore not available as part of this data summary. Instrument scientist: Stephane Bauguitte (UEA, Norwich).
- **PAN ECGC's:** Data are not included in this report but will be made available at a later date. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent (UK Met. Office).
- **Bottles:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section to see when these were filled). Bottle filler: David Tiddeman (UK Met. Office).

ARASF

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